

Appendix B: Interview-Handout AI Act High-Risk Requirements Summary

This is a concise summary of the requirements set out for high-risk AI systems by the AI Act (Articles 8 to 17). It is based on the European Parliament's negotiating position from 14 June 2023 ¹. This is what we shared with the respondents before the interviews.

Risk & quality management system (Art 9 and 17)

- Foster adequate design & development of the system for the minimization of identified risks.
- Post-market monitoring system.
- Testing procedures:
 - Compliance with all requirements.
 - Consistent performance in line with the system's intended purpose.

Data governance (Art 10)

- Quality criteria for training, validation and testing data.
- Bias detection and mitigation.
- Transfer context bias prevention.
- Data gap and shortcomings identification.
- Data vetting for errors, as well as fostering relevancy, representativeness, and completeness of the data.

Accuracy, robustness, and cybersecurity (Art 15)

- Goal: consistent performance throughout the lifecycle while guaranteeing resilience against attacks.
- Resilience against the exploitation of system vulnerabilities by unauthorized third parties that could influence system's performance, outputs, behavior, or use in general.
- Types of attacks to be counteracted: data and model poisoning; adversarial examples; model evasion; confidentiality attacks; and model flaws.
- Technical & organizational measures against possible errors, faults, and inconsistencies.
- Robustness through both user input and technical redundancy in the form of backups or fail-safe plans.
- Avoidance of negative feedback loops for continuous learning systems → mitigation measures against possibly biased outputs as new input and against malicious input manipulation in general.

Transparency and provision of information (Art 13)

- State tested and validated level of accuracy, robustness, and cybersecurity.
- Users must reasonably understand system's functioning and what data is processed.
- Interpretability of output.
- State degree to which explanations for system's decisions can be made.
- Right to explanation of individual decision-making (only for AI system's decisions that produce legal effects for the affected person or similarly severe impacts, like health, safety, fundamental rights, or socio-economic well-being):
 - Role of the AI system in decision.
 - Main parameters of decision.
 - Related input data.

Human oversight (Art 14)

- Appropriate human-machine interfaces for effective human oversight, proportionate to the risks involved.

Record-keeping (Art 12)

- Automatic logging:
 - Ensure traceability throughout the entire system lifetime.
 - Also includes logging of the system's environmental impact concerning energy consumption and resource use.

Technical documentation (Art 11)

¹P9_TA(2023)0236. Online available: https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/TA-9-2023-0236_EN.html (Jun 2023)